

Mapping the Network: Assessing Mobile Data Signal Strength and Coverage Gaps for Reliable Connectivity of College Students in Bulacan State University – Main Campus

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Abstract

This study is conducted to map the network coverage strength and gaps within the premises of Bulacan State University – Main Campus. Its sole purpose is to provide reliable connectivity for college students within the school premises. A sequential mixed-methods approach is employed to ensure that both statistical and descriptive data are analyzed appropriately. Different instruments, such as Likert-scale survey, Net Monitor Cell Signal Logging Pro, and open-ended questionnaires, are used to identify areas within the campus with strong signals and coverage gaps, as well as to measure the reliability of connectivity across different locations within the institution. A total of 294 students served as respondents in conducting the study. These participants answered the Likert scale survey and open-ended questionnaires about reliable connectivity, with the generated heat maps as their reference material. Lastly, this research made use of statistical and thematic data analysis methods to interpret both numerical and descriptive information collected during the fieldwork.

Keywords: Internet Service Providers (ISPs), Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP), decibel-milliwatts (dBm), Network Coverage Mapping, Signal

Strength, Coverage Gaps, Mobile Data Reliability, Mixed-method Research, Net Monitor Cell Signal Logging Pro, Digital Learning Infrastructure

Introduction

In recent years, the development of technology has led to increased convenience and dependence on mobile devices for communication and information access. Devices such as smartphones, laptops, tablets, and other portable gadgets have become an intrinsic part of daily life, allowing people to connect instantly through social media, communication platforms, and collaborative softwares. According to Frost (2023), communication has been made more convenient through the use of technology. We can now communicate and converse with others instantly, no matter where they are across the globe. It has indisputably revolutionized the way people interact with each other—even in familiar or private settings. Apart from communication, these devices have also transmuted how people gather and disseminate information daily—providing access to vast amounts of information through online browsing. As stated by Iacovitti (2022), virtual technologies involve representing any kind of message by means of strings of numerical symbols; this makes relaying and storage of information efficient and adaptable. Moreover, in the context of education, technology has become a method for institutions to distribute tasks and resources to students online. As mentioned by Swenson (2020), the materials available today have made it possible to learn, share, and create easily in a multi-national setting. Technologies have also provided educators with options of teaching strategies—a few of them include mobile educational apps, virtual reality, collaborative platforms, and many other tools and methods, which serve as

alternatives to accommodate students during emergencies or urgent situations (Paine, 2024).

On the other hand, this rapid growth of technology has also spurred the advancement of mobile internet, wherein signal strength plays a crucial role in maximizing its use. As stated by Zontou (2023), the development of cellular networks has been pivotal in shaping the field of modern telecommunications. These mobile networks have significantly helped people interact with each other. Moreover, the growth of mobile networks has fueled the rise of social media and other digital platforms, allowing individuals to convey information and establish connections globally without any geographical limitations. The accessibility of these mobile connections has improved through various Internet Service Providers (ISPs). These internet providers promote users to browse the web, watch movies, shop online, and more, all for a subscription or membership fee. Beyond basic connectivity, ISPs often enhance their value proposition by providing services like email, domain registration, web hosting, and even browser packages (Twin, 2025). However, the reliance on technology and mobile internet also highlights the need for reliable coverage of mobile data signals, as inconsistent cellular networks occur due to various factors. As stated by Baker (2024), the materials used for the construction of buildings can significantly influence mobile signal strength. Materials such as concrete, metal, and multiple-paned glass windows frequently hinder or weaken radio frequencies, leading to poor signal penetration—providing difficulty in

communication and work efficiency. These gaps in network coverage pose a problem for acquiring better signals in various settings. They hinder communication and information exchange, making it difficult to achieve reliable connectivity in daily life.

At state universities across the Philippines, students report frequent issues with unstable data coverages and limited bandwidth. While 94% of students have some form of internet access, many still struggle with slow or unreliable connections that disrupt their online learning experiences and hinder academic performance (Asio et al., 2021, as cited in Carlos et al., 2024). Relating this matter to Bulacan State University (BulSU) – Main Campus, local studies conducted in this institution state the same issue of inconsistent network connectivity within the campus. As stated by Carlos et al. (2024), university facilities like the e-library and online platforms depend heavily on a consistent internet connection. However, constant connectivity issues have led many students to use mobile data as an alternative. Additionally, a study on campus Wi-Fi connectivity conducted by Easha et al. (2020) highlights that conventional educational institutions in the modern day provide at least limited campus Wi-Fi coverage, for both the teaching staff and students to access university portals, avail study materials, and view online resources. In the context of BulSU, certain areas are known to have weak or unstable signals, which hinder students' ability to fully utilize online materials, communicate effectively, and accomplish academic requirements. This

challenge is especially critical at this time when digital platforms are incorporated into teaching methods and modes of learning. The lack of reliable network coverage affects not only academic aspects but also daily student life, as many rely on stable internet access for communication and information exchange. Thus, people need to be aware of the places with strong signals and coverage gaps.

Strengthening a community rooted with reliable connectivity through mobile data connections is crucial. However, it is challenging due to infrastructure that causes signal jams and coverage gaps. Therefore, this study aims to assess signal strength in Bulacan State University through network coverage mapping in order to locate places where the quality or state of being connected within the campus is reliable. As mentioned by Pradeepa et al. (2022), network coverage mapping is a technique used to locate and illustrate physical and virtual network connectivity via a group of related tasks that aid the creation of a network coverage map. Through this, the researchers are able to determine the places in the institution with strong signals and coverage gaps. This study holds significance in addressing a practical concern that impacts the institution's pursuit of a systematic and technology-driven learning environment. Due to the emergence of flexible learning at BulSU, it is essential for the academe to gain insight regarding signal strength in various buildings, especially for communication and information exchange.

Upon conducting this study, it is expected that the results have provided valuable

insights for students by identifying specific areas on campus where the mobile signal is strong and where coverage gaps exist. This information allowed students to maximize their use of online resources and accomplish digital academic tasks without unnecessary disruptions. Furthermore, the data can be used by the university administration to promote reliable connectivity by using the study as a signal indicator. According to the GSMA (2025), equal learning opportunities and a digitally inclusive environment critically require a good mobile service in technological settings. The study could also help create a more commodious learning environment where students' learning and productivity aren't hindered by poor connectivity. Ultimately, the heat map tool can be integrated into the institution's digital student portal. Regular updates to the map would allow administrators to monitor emerging coverage gaps, and track improvements regarding signal strength after building renovations.

Objectives

This study aims to assess the signal strength in certain areas of BulSU through network coverage mapping to pinpoint specific buildings or areas with strong signal or a coverage gap. Its goal is to address the issues related to unreliable connectivity within the campus, which affects the students' learning and communication. This study revolves around (1) measuring the signal strength and coverage gaps of different ISPs in various areas in the campus, (2) assessing how these certain ISPs may affect signal strength, (3) identifying which ISPs are suitable in specific locations, and (4)

determining how network coverage mapping can help attain reliable connectivity.

Methods

Research Design

This research has employed a mixed-methods research approach in a sequential order, wherein the researchers first utilized quantitative methods, as numerical data formed the basis of the study's results. The primary instrument to be used in gathering quantitative data is an Android app known as Net Monitor Cell Signal Logging Pro. This application renders various features, including the collection of mobile data signal measures such as Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP), Global Positioning System (GPS) data, and other cellular system measurements, which are essential in administering the research (Maurice & Ray, 2021). In this study, the RSRP values of each ISP (DITO, GLOBE, and SMART) is measured in decibel-milliwatts (dBm) with the use of Net Monitor Cell Signal Logging Pro, and the results are interpreted through visual graphs—specifically a signal coverage heat map. Moreover, a 20-item Likert scale survey is used in this study, wherein the respondents are given a questionnaire before and after the experiment proper. The pre-experiment survey are divided into four sections: Internet Service Providers (ISPs), Student Experiences Regarding Network Connectivity, Areas of Coverage Gaps, and Areas with Strong Connection. The post-experiment survey also consisted of four sections, these sections centers around the assistance of the generated heat map in navigating the following: Accuracy of the Heat Map: Most

Suitable Internet Service Provider (ISP), Assessing the Help of the Generated Heat Map, Reliable Connectivity, and Usability and Accessibility of the Heat Map. The validity and reliability of these surveys are tested through pilot testing, wherein the researchers made use of a small group to run through the survey questionnaires. The researchers have also generated a heat map, which displayed the areas where good, fair, and poor signals occur for each ISP.

After collecting the numerical data needed for the study, the researchers then incorporated qualitative methods to expound on the quantitative results of the study. The researchers have asked new set of respondents open-ended questions about (1) the accuracy of the heat map concerning places with strong signals and coverage gaps, as well as (2) the help of this heat map in achieving reliable connectivity across the campus. Directly integrating both methodologies allows the researchers to strengthen the numerical results of the study by expounding it using descriptive data. Overall, these instruments provided meaningful insights about students' perspectives and experiences regarding areas of strong signals and coverage gaps.

Participants

This study have applied both stratified sampling and purposive sampling to determine the total number of respondents. The students are divided into strata using stratified sampling, with each stratum formed based on their respective colleges. Purposive sampling is then be employed by choosing respondents from each college that satisfy

the criteria required for the study—wherein at least one student per college building must comply. Within these selected respondents, each must use at least one of the following ISPs: DITO, GLOBE, and SMART. To ensure the accuracy of the study, the sample size is calculated using Raosoft® (Sample Size Calculator; Raosoft Inc.), with a 6.3% margin of error, 95% confidence level, and 50% response rate. Considering an approximate number of 30,000 students in the institution, the required sample size needed for the quantitative process of the study is 241 students from the main campus (Velez, 2023).

Since the institution has thirteen colleges, the study has included a total of 13 students who participated in the open-ended questionnaires provided after the quantitative process of the study. Essentially, the research utilized 254 students from the main campus, representing each college and year level. In administering the study, the researchers have made use of an imbalance approach in selecting the respondents. By employing this approach, the researchers would be able to emphasize the diversity of the experiences of the students regarding network connectivity rather than dividing the colleges into equal groups of ISPs. Moreover, this approach allowed the researchers to choose respondents who are more exposed to the mobile data connectivity occurrence, ensuring more authentic insights.

Since the study revolves around signal connectivity within BulSU, the respondents consisted of students who

often use mobile data or embedded Subscriber Identity Modules (eSIMs) for school activities such as online classes, research, and communication. Only students who are officially enrolled and who regularly use their mobile data on campus are included. Students who do not use any ISP on campus or are currently on leave of absence are not included in the study. Lastly, students who have or are taking a postgraduate degree are not included in the experiment. As stated by Finetti (2022), the range of people with higher education past the undergraduate degree is known as postgraduates. This includes both masteral and doctoral degrees. Thus, students, especially from the College of Law, are not considered as qualified for the research.

Data Collection

In order to properly conduct the study, the researchers have observed a chronological data-gathering procedure. The researchers first finalized the survey questionnaire and prepare the applications necessary for mobile data signal strength mapping to ensure that the instruments are ready for implementation, wherein the selection of participants then followed. The survey is then administered to the selected respondents before and after the study. The research has utilized a Likert scale survey consisting of five points, ranging from strongly agree (5) to strongly disagree (1). This enabled the respondents to convey how much they agree or disagree with a specific statement (McLeod, 2023). The items focused on students' experiences with internet connectivity, including how often weak signals occur, where these are usually

encountered, and which ISPs are suitable for each area. To ensure reliability and validity, participants are encouraged to answer with honesty.

Besides the Likert scale survey, signal mapping is also conducted across various areas of the campus by the researchers. Mobile devices, along with an application that measures mobile data signal is used by the researchers in gathering actual signal readings in various locations such as college buildings, the E-library, canteens, and open spaces. The measurements are collected at specific times of the day, specifically morning and afternoon—to anticipate variations across the day and strengthen the validity of data by accurately representing signal fluctuations; the analysis of signal strength and coverage gaps then followed after the said collection. The recorded signal strength measurements of the network coverage mapping that was done by the researchers is then summarized and mapped to highlight connectivity levels across the campus. The results are presented through visual graphs and campus heat maps that allow for clear interpretation, which are then posted to the respective respondents as a reference.

After posting the results of the network coverage mapping, the researchers then conducted a post-experiment Likert scale survey to the same respondents who have answered the pre-experiment survey. This allowed the researchers to measure the reliability of the network coverage map regarding the strong signals and coverage gaps measured around the campus. The items in the post-experiment survey focused on how the coverage map has

helped them in achieving reliable connectivity, how accurate the signal coverage indicated in the map is in terms of strong signals and coverage gaps, as well as how this map has assisted them in using the most suitable ISP around the campus. The survey responses is then tabulated and converted into numerical values based on the Likert scale. In cases of non-responses or incomplete survey data, the researchers have conducted follow-ups with participants and exclude consistently missing responses from the analysis to avoid bias.

Upon analyzing the results from the quantitative instruments, the researchers then administered open-ended questionnaires to another set of participants. Employing this qualitative instrument on the numerical results of the study allowed the researchers to further strengthen the study's results. The gathered data from the two methodologies is then analyzed to identify patterns between perceived experiences and actual readings.

These findings served as the basis for drawing conclusions and formulating recommendations aimed at improving the acquisition of reliable internet connectivity. This study solely aims to map areas where strong signals and coverage gaps occur, determine which ISPs are most suitable in each location, and illustrate how the network map could help students achieve reliable connectivity within the campus. It did not measure how coverage gaps affect students' academic performance, nor it examined the financial limitations posed by mobile networks. It also did not include how types or models

of mobile devices may affect signal coverage. The study was also focused solely on Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP), which evaluates the strength of the received signal from the mobile data cell tower. Essentially, it also measured how strong the connection is between a person's gadget (e.g., smartphone) and the primary cell tower the person is connected to. Thus, it did not tackle the interventions, RSSI, RSRQ, and noise that affect the quality of the signal, but rather, the main signal strength only that the signal towers provide (Ramirez, 2023).

Data Analysis

This study focused on the quantitative data collected using the NetMonitor Cell Signal Logging Pro app, which measures the signal strength in dBm for each ISP, together with the results of a Likert scale survey. It aims to identify which parts of BulSU have strong signal coverage and which areas come across weak connections. To ensure the interpretation is correct, the statistical methods used are directly aligned with the study's goals. Through statistical analysis, the researchers are able to see patterns, variations, and trends in signal strength across the campus. As Vandever (2020) noted, using statistics is essential in studies aiming to draw numerical conclusions, as it helps reduce errors and make results more accurate. For this reason, the study calculated the weighted mean of the students' answers in the closed-ended surveys to identify the mean score, which became the basis for forming conclusions. The Likert scale survey results was also presented using actual number distributions to clearly show how

many students agreed or disagreed with certain statements about campus signal.

Aside from the survey and signal data, interviews are also conducted, and the answers are examined through thematic analysis. Kiger and Varpio (2020) described thematic analysis as a way of finding and organizing patterned ideas or themes from responses. In this research, students' answers in the open-ended questions regarding the places with strong and weak signals are coded, and grouped into themes. By using thematic analysis, the study can highlight the real-life situations of students when it comes to connectivity. The use of weighted means allowed the study to account for varying student sample sizes across locations, producing more accurate comparisons of network performance. Complementing this, thematic coding of interview responses revealed recurring issues—such as inconsistent coverage and unstable connection—that help explain the variability observed in the numerical results. This part of the research reinforced the statistical results by providing real-time explanations of the existence of certain patterns and how these affect the university community.

Results

Pre-experiment Survey

Table 1.1 Internet Service Providers

QUESTIONS	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Weighted Mean
I know which areas within the school campus have the strongest internet signal.	23	79	71	52	16	3.18
I can identify places where my ISP performs poorly.	61	103	49	24	4	3.80

I know which college buildings provide the most consistent connection quality.	32	81	73	47	8	3.34
I know which ISP offers the best performance in my area.	29	94	72	37	9	3.40
I experience minimal disconnections or network interruptions with my ISP.	66	80	34	35	26	3.66
TOTAL						3.48

Table 1.1 illustrates that the majority of the students have neutral opinions about the signal strength of their internet service providers (ISPs) within the campus. This means that many students are not exactly aware of which areas have strong or weak signals for their ISPs. Consequently, this lack of knowledge could affect their ability to identify optimal spots for better connectivity within the school premises.

Table 1.2 Student Experiences Regarding Network Connectivity

QUESTIONS	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Weighted Mean
I often experience delays when loading web pages or online materials on campus.	128	86	24	2	1	4.40
The mobile connection inside the campus is inconsistent throughout the day.	126	78	29	7	1	4.33
Physical barriers, such as thick walls or distance from the specific location, contribute to coverage gaps.	70	108	60	2	1	4.01
Most areas on campus have little to no mobile data coverage.	94	86	47	14	0	4.08
The type of mobile network provider I use affects my connectivity within the university.	76	99	54	9	3	3.99

Table 1.2 displays that most students agree that the presence of coverage gaps within the campus is evident. This suggests that many students experience weak or unreliable connectivity in certain

areas, which makes it difficult for them to identify where their ISP provides a strong or reliable mobile data signal.

Table 1.3 Areas of Coverage Gaps

QUESTIONS	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Weighted Mean
There are parts of the campus where there is no signal at all.	137	74	26	3	1	4.42
Coverage gaps on campus cause inconvenience when communicating or doing online work.	145	72	23	0	1	4.49
Certain classrooms or hallways have extremely weak or no network connection, which causes disruptions during online classes.	125	86	27	2	1	4.38
The presence of coverage gaps affects my productivity and learning experience.	106	91	38	6	0	4.23

Table 1.3 shows that most students agree that several areas within the campus have weak or unreliable mobile data signals. This issue affects the ability of students to stay connected online, whether for academic purposes, communication, or personal use.

Table 1.4 Areas with Strong Signal

QUESTIONS	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Weighted Mean
There are specific areas in the university where the internet connection is consistently strong.	43	97	60	33	8	3.56
I am satisfied with the network performance in areas with strong connectivity.	39	85	61	33	23	3.35
Some buildings in the campus have noticeably stronger network signals than others.	46	109	70	11	5	3.75
Strong network coverage is available in open spaces such as the Heroes Park, Booth hallways, and College benches.	39	82	85	25	10	3.48

Overall, the campus has several locations with consistently strong and reliable internet connections.	36	79	72	41	13	3.35
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Table 1.4 illustrates that most students have a neutral opinion regarding several areas within the campus that have strong or reliable mobile data signals. This means that the students are also unaware of the various locations within the campus that are not affected by coverage gaps.

Generated Heat Maps per ISP

Figure 1.1 Signal Distribution of DITO

Figure 1.1 exhibits the signal strength distribution of DITO across the campus from morning to afternoon. It shows how DITO’s signal strength is specifically stronger in the College of Engineering Building 2 and the Student Lounge, while it is poor across the Roxas Hall and the Alvarado Hall.

Figure 1.2 Signal Distribution of GLOBE

Figure 1.2 presents the signal strength distribution of GLOBE within the campus from morning to afternoon. It shows that GLOBE's signal is significantly strong across different locations in the institution. It illustrates a strong coverage of GLOBE's mobile data signal at all times within the campus.

Figure 1.3 Signal Distribution of SMART

Figure 1.3 unveils the signal strength distribution of SMART across the campus from morning to afternoon. It shows that SMART's signal is specifically stronger in the College of Engineering Building 2, the Student Lounge, the CBEA Building, and the Flores Hall, while it is poor across Gate 2 and the Alvarado Hall.

Figure 2.1 Overall Variability of DITO

Figure 2.1 illustrates the overall results of DITO across the campus from morning to afternoon.

Figure 2.2 Overall Variability of GLOBE

Figure 2.2 illustrates the overall results of GLOBE across the campus from morning to afternoon.

Figure 2.3 Overall Variability of SMART

Figure 2.3 illustrates the overall results of SMART across the campus from morning to afternoon.

Post-experiment Survey

Table 2.1 Accuracy of the Heat Map: Most Suitable Internet Service Provider (ISP)

QUESTIONS	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Weighted Mean
The Heat Map provided greatly reflects how various ISPs perform on the campus	118	111	12	0	0	4.44
The heat map accurately reflects the actual performance of ISPs in different areas.	90	137	11	3	0	4.30
It is now easy to navigate the areas suitable for my chosen ISP	98	127	13	2	0	4.32

The generated heat map from the study has helped me in navigating the most suitable ISP in different locations.	90	133	15	2	0	4.28
The results in the signal mapping changed how I perceive the performance of various ISPs.	99	118	23	1	0	4.31
TOTAL						4.33

Table 2.1 demonstrates that the majority of the students strongly agree that the heat map is accurate and helps identify the most suitable internet service provider (ISP) across different locations within the campus. This indicates that students find the heat map dependable and reliable in showing which ISP offers the best connectivity in different areas.

Table 2.2 Assessing the Help of the Generated Heat Map

QUESTIONS	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Weighted Mean
Because of the Heat Map provided, it is now much easier to locate the areas where the signal is strong and poor	90	140	8	3	0	4.32
I can now identify the places where signal strength and coverage gaps occur	125	108	7	1	0	4.48
I am aware of which ISP performs best in different parts of the university.	98	125	13	5	0	4.31
I can identify the most suitable ISPs for different buildings based on the map.	102	135	13	1	0	4.53
The visual representation of signal data made it easier to understand coverage.	126	97	16	2	0	4.44
TOTAL						4.42

Table 2.2 states that a large majority of the students strongly agree that the heat map has helped find areas with good mobile data signal strength. This suggests

that the heat map effectively guides students to locations where they can experience better connectivity for their online activities.

Table 2.3 Reliable Connectivity

QUESTIONS	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Weighted Mean
The heat map helped me experience fewer internet interruptions.	71	134	30	5	0	4.11
I can now identify which locations have the most reliable internet connection.	120	105	13	3	0	4.43
The study increased my awareness of how connection reliability varies per location.	107	115	14	5	0	4.34
The generated heat map supports better digital communication within the campus.	91	129	19	2	0	4.28
The Heat Map contributed in achieving reliable connectivity within the campus	97	122	21	1	0	4.31

Table 2.3 illustrates that most students strongly agree that the heat map provides reliable connectivity. This indicates that the students find the heat map as a reliable tool for achieving stable mobile data connectivity within the campus.

Table 2.4 Usability and Accessibility of the Heat Map

QUESTIONS	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Weighted Mean
I am satisfied with how the heat map presents information.	100	119	18	4	0	4.31
The heat map was easy to access and understand.	104	101	33	3	0	4.27
The interface or design of the heat map made it engaging to use.	105	94	39	3	0	4.25

I use the heat map results to choose the best location for my internet connection.	72	107	49	12	0	3.98
I can easily interpret the color representations in the heat map.	117	102	19	3	0	4.38
TOTAL						4.24

Table 2.4 shows that the majority of the students agree with the usability and accessibility of the heat map. This means that students find the heat map easy to use and access, allowing them to conveniently check for strong signal areas whenever needed.

Qualitative Results

Accuracy and Reliability of the Heat Map. The respondents agreed that the heat map provided by the researchers was accurate and reliable—demonstrating their actual experiences with mobile data signal strength on campus. Several participants mentioned that the areas they found to have strong or weak connectivity matched closely with the heat map, suggesting that the researchers’ representation accurately reflected the actual network conditions. Numerous students also emphasized that the map aligned with their experiences across different ISPs (DITO, GLOBE, SMART), and that it consistently illustrated which areas recommended stronger or weaker signals. While some of the respondents acknowledged that minor dissimilarities could occur due to device type or network crowding, the overall insight was that the heat map could be a reliable visual guide for campus connectivity.

Strong and Weak Signal Areas. The respondents were able to identify particular areas on campus where the network was consistently strong or weak, which is highly similar to the heat map. The most frequently stated areas with strong signals were the College of Engineering Building 2, the Student Lounge, the CSSP Building, Gates 3 and 4, the Federizo Hall, and various floors of the E-Library. However, poor connectivity was recurrently mentioned across the Natividad Hall, the Roxas Hall, and places around the Valencia Hall. Participants stated that the heat maps were a useful tool for identifying these locations, making it simpler and more convenient to determine where the connectivity was most reliable and where issues were most noticeable.

Usefulness of the Heat Map for Students. The respondents stated that the heat map helped them navigate the campus and find stable network access easier, saving time and effort when looking for locations with reliable connectivity for online learning, research, or communication. Many participants mentioned that the heat maps helped them schedule more efficiently for activities that required internet connectivity, especially online classes and virtual collaborations. As a result, students saw the maps as a great resource for optimizing their internet access and connectivity across campus.

Variability of ISP Performance. Several respondents suggested that network performance varied based on the ISP chosen. For example, SMART was shown to give better internet connectivity in

specific areas, whereas DITO performed poorly in those same areas. Meanwhile, GLOBE was widely considered to provide the most constant coverage across campus. Students noticed that the heat maps highlighted these variances—suggesting the impact of ISP selection and school location on connectivity. These findings emphasize the fact that students' experiences with internet connection might vary depending on their ISP, and that displaying this variation is critical for detecting coverage gaps and improving internet connectivity.

“The heat map provided shows that some ISP performs well, while some ISP performs poorly within the campus, does the results of the heat map correspond with your experience? Why?”

“Yes, because the heat map corresponds accurately to the service providers I use, which are DITO and SMART. wherein DITO has poor signal strength in Natividad Hall and SMART has a better signal strength than it.” - Participant 1

“Yes, I've been using the GLOBE network, and the signal strength I get is pretty much the same as what the map shows.” - Participant 2

Environmental and Device Factors Affecting Signal. A small number of respondents mentioned that the type of device used and the level of network crowding could have an impact on signal strength. While the heat maps largely correlated with students' experiences, these exogenous factors occasionally caused connection issues. Participants stated that, while the map is useful for detecting strong and weak signal

locations, the actual reading may vary slightly based on the environment and device capabilities. These findings emphasize the heat maps' possible shortcomings and identify areas for improvement in future connection research.

Conclusion

The constant coverage gaps regarding mobile data signal strength that occur within the campus gave rise to the hardships of students in finding reliable connectivity. This phenomenon burdens the students—especially during online classes—but is often overlooked. This research has been conducted for the sole purpose of devising a heat map that indicates the signal distribution across the institution—assisting the students in locating reliable connectivity. The study certainly validated that the execution of signal mapping within Bulacan State University (BulSU) – Main Campus has significantly helped the students in assessing signal strength within different locations.

Signal Strength and Coverage Gaps. The study has concluded that the campus consists of various places where signal strength may be weak or strong. Moreover, it has also been highlighted that the students are unaware of these locations—contributing to the intervention of information exchange and communication within the institution.

Reliable Connectivity. The creation of the signal heat map has significantly assisted the students in obtaining reliable connectivity across the campus. It has lessened the network interruptions experienced by the students, and it has

also contributed in building the knowledge of the students regarding the locations with strong signals and coverage gaps.

Variability of Network. Conducting signal mapping across the institution has also emphasized that the variety of Internet Service Providers (ISPs) influences mobile data signal strength. Certain ISPs may provide a strong signal in a specific area, while some ISPs, on the other hand, may supply a weak signal—indicating that signal strength may vary depending on which ISP a person is using.

Most Suitable Internet Service Provider (ISP). Based on the signal mapping conducted by the researchers, the most reliable ISP inside the institution is GLOBE, followed by SMART, then DITO. Despite each ISP having a certain place where coverage gaps may occur—GLOBE has provided a strong signal in multiple places where the other ISPs have failed to do so. Thus, GLOBE is the most recommended ISP to utilize within the BulSU - Main Campus.

Overall, this study demonstrates that assessing the signal strengths and coverage gaps of various ISPs across the campus has provided awareness to the students regarding the areas within the institution where reliable connectivity may be achieved. It offers a unique contribution by integrating mobile data signal mapping with student-reported connectivity experiences. By merging numerical measurements and descriptive data, the research provides a more comprehensive assessment of campus network coverage that provides assistance

for students. The creation of a signal heat map has served as a tool for students in harnessing a community with fewer signal interruptions. This has enhanced the students' ability to locate the areas with strong and weak signals—contributing in resolving the problems regarding information exchange and communication across the campus.

Recommendations

Derived from the findings and conclusions of this study, the succeeding recommendations are proposed to further improve mobile data signal strength and connectivity within the Bulacan State University - Main Campus:

Infrastructure Improvement. The university administration, in collaboration with Internet Service Providers (ISPs), should consider implementing additional cellular repeaters or signal boosters in areas identified with poor connectivity, such as Natividad Hall, Roxas Hall, and the vicinity of Valencia Hall. This would help minimize coverage gaps and ensure more uniform signal distribution across the campus.

Integration of Heat Map into Campus Systems. The generated heat map should be made accessible through the university's online portal, bulletin boards, or social media pages. This would guide students and staff in identifying areas with reliable connectivity for academic and communication purposes.

Partnership with ISPs. The institution should collaborate with major ISPs—particularly DITO, GLOBE, and SMART—to evaluate network performance and

identify technical solutions for zones with coverage gaps. Regular assessments can help maintain optimal signal strength and service reliability.

Future Research. Future studies may expand on this research by including other factors affecting mobile signal performance, such as bandwidth usage, device compatibility, or environmental interruptions. Additionally, researchers may explore how connectivity impacts academic productivity, digital learning efficiency, and overall student satisfaction. Future studies may consider device-specific performance differences and environmental factors such as building materials, which may also influence signal quality. Accounting for these variables can further refine the accuracy of mobile data signal mapping.

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